

PECULARITIES OF ORGANIZING EXTRA-CURRICULAR ACTIVITIES IN TEACHING EFL

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7854352>

Jumaboyeva Nilufar Zoirovna

*An english teacher of the
school N#11 of Khazarasp*

Annotation: This article discusses in detail the peculiarities of extra-curricular activities in teaching English as a foreign language, mainly at schools, to strengthen and revise the taught material in an entertaining way.

Keywords: out of class, cultural point, collaborate, poster presentation, debates, story-telling, creativity.

Extracurricular activities (ECA) are usually defined as learners' activities that fall outside the normal curriculum of educational institution, they supplement the regular course of classroom instruction and are sometimes organized or conducted with some participation of instructors (Campbell, 1973). Although the term 'extracurricular activities' appeared only in the late 19th century, different kinds of extracurriculars have been used from the antiquity. Debates, drama, competitions (for example, oratorical or athletics) and different interest-group societies were organized in ancient Athens and Sparta in support of regular education (McKown, 1952).

In teaching a foreign language the learners are not expected to know not only the language, but also the culture of the nation which language he or she is learning. In order to gain this aim, we suggest that teachers should carry out the extra - curricular works. Teachers are expected to build the relationship between culture and language and to explore effective ways to bring a cross - cultural element into the classroom: pupils are to be aware of the following: a way of life; a system of beliefs; a shared history or set of experiences.

In Uzbekistan at schools ECA are used to teach English with enthusiasm, especially for revision. Teachers may provide their classes with ECA while they have taught the whole unit or due to special events like festivals, birthdays and other occasions. For instance, children revise taught material with the help of extra activities like making posters, learning poems, riddles by heart, making dishes or cookies, practising learned recipes. In feasts such as Halloween, New Year Party or Navruz , children may act out various dramas connected with festivals origin or customs. Here they may use taught vocabulary, feel themselves like the heroes of this feast and easily present and fix the word and phrases in their minds. It leads to cooperate with their peers at the same time.

As ECA is out of curriculum, it is planned by the teachers beforehand. They organize the activities according to the age, level, interests and topic. For instance,

Age of the pupils: 12,13

Level: Beginner

Interests: art, desining,

Topic: Forest: Wild animals

ECA: Poster presentation/ Riddles

In universities ECA are used in an extraordinary way. Students are given more different tasks rather than schoolchildren at the same time more difficult ones. They may prepare tour guide leaflets about touristic destinations, they may visit historical places like museums, mosques and enrich their historical knowledge in english by guides, besides this students may talk about this places to the tourists by themselves. It may cause them speak more in this language and practise with native speakers.

After classes teachers may utilize these kinds of extra activities in Uzbek schools.